

DECREASE IN THE SHARE OF STATE PROPERTY IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY TREND AND PRIVATIZATION OF STATE PROPERTY

Ergasheva Mohizarxon Gofurjon qizi¹

Turgunboev Ikromjon Imomidin ogli²

¹Student of Management at Andijan Machine-building institute

²Student of Economics at Andijan Machine-building institute,
Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6785697>

Annotation: The article describes what state property is and its share in the national economy, which is one of the main links in the country's economy, as well as the privatization of state property, the benefits that may result from it, the transformation of state property into private sector and priorities such as significantly increasing the scale of existing economic sectors through partnership or completion of entrepreneurs, creating a competitive environment in the domestic and foreign markets through the emerging private sectors will be highlighted, and the above ideas will be explored in more detail.

Keywords: Trends, functional, privatization, private sector, dividends, fixed assets, ownership.

The national economy is a complex economic system consisting of many interrelated economic elements. The whole set of practical relations between these elements describes the structural structure of the economy.

The national economy is an integrated economy that includes all sectors and industries, micro- and macro-level economies, functional economies, and many infrastructures. The structure of the national economy is the result of the development of the social division of labor.

State property is one of the forms of ownership, belonging to the state and all the property and property rights necessary for the performance of its functions. The concept of state property is inextricably linked with the concept of "state" and they are always interdependent. In the past, state property has increased mainly due to wars of aggression. State property included buildings and land, as well as food, horses, fodder, and more. By the time of capitalism, the government began to function in various fields (money circulation, employment, foreign trade, social protection of the poor, culture, education, etc.). In connection with this, state property also increased at the expense of schools, hospitals, monetary institutions, embassies and others. Today, the share of state-owned enterprises in developed countries varies. For example, in the United States and Japan, this amount is very low (around 2%). In Europe, state-owned enterprises produce between 10% (Germany) and 30% (Austria) of GDP. They employ 4% (UK) to 20-25% (Austria, Greece, France). State-owned enterprises

account for one-sixth of total capital investment in the economy (in Germany and the United Kingdom), one-third in France and one-half in Austria. One-third of all arable land in the United States is owned by the federal government.

In Uzbekistan, from the beginning of October until the early 1990s, before the independence of the Republic, all property, except for private and cooperative property, was state property. After independence, the inviolability of all forms of property - state property, mixed property, joint venture property, community property, joint stock property, etc. - and the creation of equal conditions for their development were enshrined in law. Accordingly, property relations will be regulated by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the Law "On Property in the Republic of Uzbekistan", which came into force on October 31, 1990, and a number of other laws. The structure and types of state property in the Republic of Uzbekistan are strictly defined. Denationalization and privatization have been chosen as the leading link in economic reforms.

Privatization of state property - the denationalization of state-owned means of production, property, enterprises, housing, vehicles, natural resources, etc. and their transfer or sale to citizens, communities, as well as to non-state legal entities; creation of various forms of property (joint, private, family, joint, mixed, corporate) on the basis of state property. Privatization of state property is carried out by transferring or selling state property to economic entities on the basis of which the property is operated on the basis of this property and assumes full property responsibility for its results on various terms and involves the change of ownership. Denationalization and privatization free transfer of property, sale of enterprises on preferential terms, sale of shares, lease of enterprises, sale of small enterprises at auction, etc. methods.

In accordance with the State Program on denationalization and deepening the process of privatization in Uzbekistan, measures have been developed to support entrepreneurship and ensure the smooth operation of enterprises in the post-privatization period. In the post-privatization period, special investment funds and banks have been set up to ensure the smooth operation of state-owned enterprises, and proceeds from privatization are being used to develop privatized enterprises. Dividends received on state-owned shares are used to renew and technically re-equip fixed assets.

Uzbekistan is undergoing targeted privatization to provide social protection and support to the poor, and to equip enterprises to produce export-oriented and competitive products. In this way, the main goal is to increase the

political and socio-economic stability of the country and to form a class of landowners who will be the backbone of the state.

List of used literature:

1. Olmasov A., Vahobov A.V. Economic theory. Textbook. - T.: "Economy and Finance", 2014. - 480 pages.
2. Khudokormov A.G. Ekonomicheskaya teoriya: Noveyshie techeniya Zapada. - M.: INFRA-M, 2009.
3. www.lex.uz - National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
4. www.edu.uz - Portal of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
5. www.worldeconomics.com